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CORROSION MECHANISM OF BIS (2HYDROXYETHYL) TEREPHTHALAMIDE

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Abstract: In this study, **bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalamide (БГТФА)** obtained by the aminolysis of secondary polyethylene terephthalate with monoethanolamine was investigated as a corrosion inhibitor. The study confirmed that **БГТФА is an environmentally acceptable compound** and can be effectively used in industry as a corrosion inhibitor for protecting metals.

Keywords: secondary polyethylene terephthalate, monoethanolamine, bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalamide, inhibitor, corrosion inhibitor, adsorption

In the chemical industry, altering the properties of the environment is considered one of the most effective methods of combating corrosion. However, in the acidic and alkaline environments of the chemical industry, corrosion remains a serious engineering challenge. To reduce the corrosion risk of metal pipelines and tanks, it is necessary to use corrosion inhibitors that slow the deterioration of metals in solutions [1]. In the present study, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) waste was used as a raw material for producing corrosion inhibitors. Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalamide (BHETA) was synthesized as the main aminolysis product. It was found that the aminolysis process was carried out using diethanolamine (DEA) as a depolymerizing agent at a PET:DEA molar ratio of 1:6 under reflux conditions. Sodium acetate was used as a catalyst, and the synthesis duration was 8 hours. It was shown that further modification of the resulting amide compound by introducing polyethylene glycol (PEG) leads to the formation of polymeric surfactants. The resulting compounds were studied as corrosion inhibitors and compared with an industrial surfactant (Surfactant II). It was found that the inhibitors synthesized on the basis of PET demonstrate higher efficiency in protecting metal from corrosion attack [2]. The bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalamide (BHTPA) molecule interacts with a metal surface through a two-step mechanism. In the first step, the molecule undergoes physical adsorption via

its hydroxyl and amide groups using van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonds. In the second step, the carbonyl and amine groups form coordination bonds with the metal atoms, forming a stable organic-inorganic interface layer (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Mechanism of BHTFA adsorption on a metal surface.

Conclusion

This study examined the effectiveness of BHTFA, obtained by aminolysis of recycled polyethylene terephthalate with monoethanolamine, in protecting metal surfaces from corrosion. The results showed that BHTFA molecules adsorb on the metal surface, forming a dense and stable protective layer. The nitrogen and oxygen atoms in the amine and amide groups of the molecule interact with the metal, effectively inhibiting the corrosion process. The resulting protective layer limits exposure to aggressive environments and improves the operational stability of the metal. The obtained data confirm the potential of BHTFA as an environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor.

References:

1. R.T. Mamajonova, Z.R. Orifov "Metallar korroziyasi va undan himoyalanih usullari to'g'risida ba'zi mulohazalar" . (2025). ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 81(2), 342-347. <https://journalss.org/index.php/obr/article/view/5502>.
4. Shima M. Elsaed .Synthesis of Some Nonionic 'olymeric Surfactants Based on Aminolized 'ET as Corrosion Inhibitors. International Journal of 'olymeric Materials 57:615-634, 2008. DOI: 10.1080/00914030801891260.